

1ST EUROPEAN
CONFERENCE
**SMALL
FOREST
HOLDINGS**

20 » 22
MAY 2025

ROME » ITALY
FAO Headquarters

PROGRAMME

V1.0

Horizon Europe SMURF project

1st European Conference on Small Forest Holdings

Rome, 20-22 May 2025

Venue: **FAO Headquarters - Red Room (CEST)**

Monday 19th : **Arrival of the participants in Rome**

PROGRAMME

Master of ceremonies:

Riccardo Castellini, Head of the International Cooperation & Forest Governance Department - Cesefor Foundation

DAY 1 (Tuesday 20th) – PLENARY

Time	Agenda Item	Speakers
Opening		
8:00 – 9:00	Registration, accreditations and conference documentation	Organizing committee
9:00 – 10:00	Conference opening & Welcome words	<p>Zhimin Wu, Forestry Director at the FAO</p> <p>Emilio Gatto, General Director for Mountain Economy and Forestry, Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forests (Italy)</p> <p>Division General Antonio Danilo Mostacchi, Commander of the Carabinieri Command for the Protection of Biodiversity (Italy)</p> <p>Elsa Enriquez Alcalde, Deputy Director General for Forestry Policy and Combating Desertification, Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (Spain)</p> <p>Pablo Sabín, CEO of the Cesefor Foundation (Spain)</p>

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Session 1 10:00-11:00 - CONFERENCE INTRODUCTIONS presented by Christophe Besacier, Coordinator of the Forest and Landscape Restoration Mechanism at FAO.

Policy, research and management

10:00 – 10:30	Keynote speeches The small private forest holdings sector: state of the art.	Luc Bouvarel , Vice President of the European Confederation of Forest Owners (CEPF) Algis Gaižutis , Board Member of the European Landowners Organization (ELO) Marko Mäki-Hakola , Chairman of the working party of forest at COPA-COGECA.
10:30 - 10:45	Key-note presentation (remote) State of knowledge and research in the sector.	Brett Butler , Small-scale Forestry Coordinator at IUFRO (U.S.A.)
10:45 - 11:00	Questions/Answers time: interactions between the audience & the panelists	
11:00 – 11:30	COFFEE BREAK & NETWORKING TIME	

Session 2 - 11:30-13:00 PANEL moderated by Alvaro Picardo, Deputy Director of Cesefor (Spain)

Legal framework and support systems for Small Forest Holdings

11:30 – 11:45	The forest legislation: state of the art	Rastislav Sulek , Forest Legislation Division Coordinator at IUFRO (Slovakia)
11:45 - 12:00	The role of the land register and the cadastral in the consolidation of forest ownership	Francisco J. Gimeno , European Land Registry Association, ELRA (Belgium)
12:00 - 12:15	Analysis and Synthesis of European forest legislation	Marta Ballesteros and Laura Vona , MILIEU Consulting (Belgium)
12:15 - 12:30	The support systems in France	Roland de Lary , General Director of the Centre National de la Propriété Forestière, CNPF (France)
12:30 - 13:00	Questions/Answers time: interactions between the audience & the panelists	
13:00 – 14:15	LUNCH BREAK	
14:15 - 14:30	Conference picture at the ground floor (main Hall)	

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Session 3 - 14:30-16:00 PANEL moderated by Prof. Juan Picos, University of Vigo (Spain).

How to maintain the sector: financial support for forest owners.

14:30 – 14:45	How the European Commission supports the private forest owners	Argyro Zerva , Team Leader for forest and forestry at DG AGRI - European Commission (Greece).
14:45 - 15:00	Financial support for the creation of forest owners' associations in Italy	Enrico Pompei , Director DIFOR II - National and International Forest Policies. Directorate General for Mountain Economy and Forests - Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forests (Italy)
15:00 - 15:15	Case study: Economical and financial elements from Germany	Dominik Bickschäfer , Ministry of Agriculture and Consumer Protection of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia (Germany)
15:15 - 15:30	Private financing and patronage for the exploitations	Carlos Marinho , Operations Manager at ANTARR Floresta e futuro (Portugal)
15:30 - 16:00	Questions/Answers time: interactions between the audience & the panelists	
16:00 – 16:30	COFFEE BREAK	

Session 4 - 16:30-18:00 ROUND TABLE presented and moderated by Inazio Martínez de Arano, European Forest Institute, EFI.

Multifunctional forests and Payment for ecosystem services (markets & incomes)

16:30 – 17:30	<p>Matthew Geraci, Milieu Consulting on behalf of the DG ENV, European Commission (Canada).</p> <p>Peter Feilberg, Executive Director of Preferred by Nature (Denmark)</p> <p>Teresa Baiges, Centre for Forest Ownership of Catalonia (Spain)</p> <p>Algis Gaizutis, Chairman at Forest and Land Owners Association of Lithuania (Lithuania)</p>
17:30 - 17:50	Questions/Answers time: interactions between the audience & the panelists

Session 5 - 18:00-18:15 - LAURUS presentation

18:00 – 18:15	The new Laurus network	Elena Moreno , Cesefor Foundation (Spain)
18:15	End of the day / Free dinner	

DAY 2 (Wednesday 21st) – MORNING PLENARY & AFTERNOON FIELD TRIP

Time	Agenda Item	Participants
Opening		
Session 6 - 9:00-10:30 PANEL moderated by Prof. João Azevedo, Bragança Polytechnic University (Portugal)		
Innovative solutions to overcome forest ownership fragmentation		
9:00 - 9:15	Forest fragmentation: causes, consequences and challenges	Davide Pettenella , Italian Society of Silviculture and Forest Ecology, SISEF (Italy)
9:15 - 10:10	EXISTING SOLUTIONS AROUND EUROPE Forest Sharing Kemijärvi jointly owned forest Fenaforesta Landscape Transformation Programme	Ilaria Zorzi , Bluebiloba (Italy) Juho Puikko , Managing Director Kemijärvi jointly owned forest (Finland) Hugo Almeida , Secretary General of Fenaforesta: National Federation of Forestry Producers' Cooperatives (Portugal)
10:10 - 10:30	Questions/Answers time: interactions between the audience & the panelists	
10:30 - 11:00	COFFEE BREAK	

Session 7 - 11:00-12:30 ROUND TABLE presented and moderated by Uwe Kies, Chair of the Wood4Bauhaus Alliance - Secretary of Innovawood.

Global value chains & new business models (living labs, product profitability, NWFP, new internal and external markets, increase in added value).

11:00 - 12:00	Round table	<p>Alexander Pinter, CEO of Holzcluster Steiermark (Austria)</p> <p>Mariana Ferreira, Luresa Resina (Spain)</p> <p>Nuno Calado, SONAE-ARAUCO (Portugal)</p> <p>Tullio Bratta, FederlegnoArredo SpA (Italy)</p>
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12:00 - 12:30 Questions/Answers time: interactions between the audience & the panelists

12:30 - 14:00 LUNCH BREAK

Field trip

14:00	<p>FIELD TRIP conducted by the University of Florence & the <i>Castelporziano</i> Presidential Estate.</p> <p> Bus transportation to Castelporziano (Departure in front of the FAO building, <i>Via delle Terme di Caracalla</i>)</p>
15:00	Arrival of the participants at the Castle
15:15	<p>Welcoming at the Castle's Square – Giulia Bonella, Head of the Estate Unit</p> <p>Projection oh the short video “An Island called Castelporziano”</p>
15:45	Guided Technical Visit: Best Practices in Sustainable Forest Management (CNS) in the Mediterranean ecosystems.
17:00	Visit at the Roman ruins of Tor Paterno Terms
18:00	Coming back to the Castle
18:00 - 20:00	Aperitive offered by the SMURF project in the garden of the Castle and networking time around the concept of the new Laurus Network
20:00 - 20:30	Transportation by bus to the City center and free dinner

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DAY 3 (Thursday 22th) – PLENARY

Time	Agenda Item	Speakers
Opening		
Session 8 - 9:00-10:30 PANEL moderated by Prof. Francesca Giannetti, University of Florence (Italy)		
Sustainable forest management answers to forest owners needs		
9:00 – 9:15	Integration of the threats and risks in forest management (fire, pests and diseases, invasive species)	Jernej Stritih , Founder and Director of the company Stritih (Slovenia)
9:15 - 9:30	Integrated models for the sustainable management of forest resources	Sara Maltoni , Member of the ANARF Scientific Committee & of the Executive Committee of the European State Forest Association (EUSTAFOR)
9:30 - 9:45	Forest owners needs	Valerie Vandenabeele , Director of Landelrijk Vlaanderen & APB-NB (Belgium)
9:45 - 10:15	<p>Closer to Nature silviculture</p> <p>Interactions with the main certification schemes</p>	<p>Francesca Giannetti, University of Florence</p> <p>Heidi Kagiali, Forestry & Conservation Manager PEFC International</p> <p>Matteo Mascolo FSC International</p>
10:15 - 10:30	Questions/Answers time: interactions between the audience & the panelists	
10:30 – 11:00	COFFEE BREAK	

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Session 9 - 11:00-12:30 FINAL ROUND TABLE & DEBATE moderated by Riccardo Castellini, Cesefor Foundation (Spain)

Political insights: how can we take what we have learned into the new European forest policies. Developing “home-take messages” from the Conference’s 3 days panels

INTERACTIONS WITH THE AUDIENCE BY MENTIMETER

11:00 – 12:45	<p>Kelsey Perlman, European Forest Campaigner at FERN (Belgium)</p> <p>Marko Mäki-Hakola, Forest director at MTK ry - Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners (Finland)</p> <p>Radek Rinn, Czech University of Life Sciences & Network of Forest extension Organizations in Europe - FOREXT (Czech Republic)</p> <p>Nathalia Formenton Cardoso, Forest Product Economic Specialist and Bioeconomy/Value Chain Expert, FAO</p> <p>Pablo Sabín, CEO of Cesefor (Spain)</p> <p>Emilio Gatto, General Director for Mountain Economy and Forestry, MASAF (Italy)</p>	
12:45 – 13:00	<p>Conference’s keynote conclusions.</p> <p>End of the event</p>	Organizing committee + Rapporteurs group
13:00 - 14:00	LUNCH AT THE FAO	Free lunch at the internal restaurants (selfpaid)

AVAILABLE TIME TO MEETING AND NETWORKING

DEPARTURE OF THE PARTICIPANTS DURING THE AFTERNOON / EVENING